

Moshe Newhouse, a Fine Arts graduate from Montclair State University in New Jersey, is [a contemporary abstract painter](#) whose work is rooted in the playfulness of oil paint.

His work is based on Old Masters paintings, which are rendered in a characteristic chiaroscuro technique. Then, he takes on these images in an inventive manner by pinching, puncturing, scratching, or mutilating the surface using knives, scalpels, heavy impasto paint and other diluent techniques. As a result- even though some of his work may look like an old master painting that has been through many changes and alterations!

In his mind-boggling paintings, [Moshe Newhouse](#) takes on different topics. He focuses on religious pieces and reinterpretations of them, such as using martyrs and saints as models for portraits and sculptures, but also landscapes (including vistas of the Lower East Side) and nature studies. His oeuvre is marked by a darker atmosphere and a certain intensity.

Moshe Newhouse's paintings [explore the body and physicality](#). By removing, changing, and adding layers to them, he intends to reveal freshness and intensity in contrast with the outer tones. He emphasizes how art functions as a representation of reality-denying classic depictions which focus only on appearances.